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Research Article

A CLINICAL STUDY ON THE BENIGN BREAST DISEASES¹Dr. Sana Ijaz, ²Dr. Ayesha Amin Cheema, ²Dr. Iqra Javaid¹Rawalpindi medical College Rawalpindi²CMH Lahore Medical College and Institute of Dentistry Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of this research work is to know about the rate of occurrence of different BBD (benign breast diseases) in the female patients of BBD in three private hospitals Rawalpindi.

Methodology: The female patients who were visiting the surgical units with various breast complications. This research work carried out at in the three private hospitals Rawalpindi and the duration of this research is from 2016 to 2018. All the female patients having breast complication were the part of this research work. The patients having cancers, carcinoma and other dangerous abnormalities excluded from this research work.

Results: Two hundred and seventy-five participants were the participants of this research work. Forty-four percent participants were from twenty-one years to thirty years of age. Thirty-three percent patients were from thirty-one to forty years of age. The most frequent BBD was fibro adenoma which discovered in seventy-five participants. Fibrocystic disorder was the next common BBD which found in fifty-seven participants.

Conclusion: Females have to suffer different BBD (Benign Breast Diseases) after achieving the age of puberty. The most common BBD is fibro adenoma which is available in the patients of twenty-one to forty year of age. The next common disease was fibrocystic BBD. The incidence of this disease found increasing with the increase of the female ages.

Key Words: disorder, Benign, Fibro adenoma disease, Fibrocystic, surgical.

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INTRODUCTION:

A heterogeneous group of abrasions is the part of the BBD (benign breast diseases) which is available with many common signs and incidentally, it is discoverable with the help of microscope [1]. All the non-cancer patients of the breast diseases included in the benign breast diseases as discharge from nipples and benign tumours. The cause and occurrence of the benign tumours change, those cannot increase the danger of developing cancer and abrasions which are the cause of fifty percent of cancer cases [2]. The mass of palpable, inversion of nipple, discharge and pain in nipples are the presentations of benign breast diseases.

The complications due to the benign breast diseases are ignorable and ill treatable as well as compared to the malignant cases. But the fact is that a large number of breast abrasions are benign breast diseases and it gives the conclusion that a large number of abrasions are the result of benign breast diseases than the malignant cases [1, 3]. We found conclusion that ninety percent patients who are visiting the surgical units are suffering of non-malignant complications [4, 5]. So, it considered beneficial to conclude the range of benign breast diseases in this area of the country. The main aim of this research work is to conclude the rate of the different benign breast diseases in the female patients visiting the private hospitals located in Hyderabad city.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work carried out at in the three private hospitals Rawalpindi and the duration of this research is from 2016 to 2018. All the females who were visiting the surgical units of these hospitals suffering of breast complications included in this research work. The patients found with malignancy or carcinomas separated from this research work.

Elaborate background histories of the patients saved in record including age, age at the time of first

pregnancy, age at the time of first menses and marital status. The patients whose age was more than fifty years and they were free from menses from two years were postmenopausal. The background histories of the whole family regarding the diseases of breast were included in records. Elaborate check-ups of axilla & lump carried to find any symptom of malignancy in the participating cases. Ultrasonography/mammograms also carried out at the time of requirement. FNAC (fine needle aspiration cytology) carried out on the patients to confirm the presence of lumps. Biopsy complied on the patients who were not discoverable in the report of FNAC. The information gathered on a special prepared Performa. The rates of different benign breast diseases in the patients of different ages evaluated.

RESULTS:

Two hundred and seventy-five patients were the participants of this research work. One hundred and twenty patients were twenty-one to thirty year of age, thirty-three percent participants were from thirty-one to forty year of age, eleven percent patients were from forty-one to fifty year of age and 10.5% patients were from eleven to twenty year of age. The most common BBD was fibro adenoma which had found in seventy-five patients. Fibrocystic BBD discovered in fifty-seven patients. Forty-five patients discovered with breast abscess. Twelve percent patients discovered with duct ectasia and mastalgia discovered in thirty-one patients. Duct papilloma discovered in thirteen patients, galactocele discovered in seven patients and tuberculosis mastitis discovered in eleven patients.

Most of the patients suffering of BBD were from third and fourth decade of their lives. Patients from different age groups were suffering of different types of BBD. Fifty-seven percent patients of BBD found in the age group of thirty-one to forty year of age. An elaborate description of the benign breast diseases in accordance with their age group is mentioned in Table-1.

S. No	Disease	Age (in years)					Total
		1 - 20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	
1	Fibro adenoma	24	43	7	1	-	75
2	Breast Abscess	3	26	15	1	-	45
3	Mastalgia	2	14	11	4	-	31
4	Tuberculosis mastitis	-	6	4	1	-	11
5	Duct Papilloma	-	6	6	-	1	13
6	Galactocele	-	3	4	-	-	7
7	Duct ectasia	-	12	13	9	-	34
8	Fibrocystic diseases	-	10	29	15	3	57
9	Fat Necrosis	-	-	2	-	-	2
Total		29	120	91	31	4	275

DISCUSSION:

Breast a very sensitive structure and different physical changes occur in its condition during various development periods. These occurrences of the physical variations generate an idea of ANDI (aberration of normal development and involution). It does not show that benign breast diseases are not occurring but this special term for those complications which are mild in nature. In this research work, eighty-two percent patients of benign breast diseases were from eleven to forty year of age with a high occurrence in the age group of twenty-one to thirty years of age.

The outcomes of this research work were similar to the research work of Out AA6 which showed that a large number of patients were from below thirty year of age. Ihekwa Proved in his research work that More than eighty percent cases of benign breast diseases were from sixteen to thirty-five year of age in Western Africa [7]. Chaudhary also concluded the same occurrence of benign breast diseases in the age group of third and fourth decade [8]. Dunn was showed different outcomes from the mentioned research works in which the average age of the patients of benign breast diseases was fifty years [9]. Fibro adenoma was the most frequent benign breast

disease which was discovered in seventy-five patients. Seventy-five percent of this disease fibro adenoma was found in the patient of age group of third decade of their life. These results were also proved by two other research works which described that the most common benign breast disease is fibro adenoma [10, 11]. Murillo found the Thirty-eight percent occurrence of fibro adenoma in his research work of six hundred and ninety-eight patients of benign breast diseases [4].

No disparity regarding the age of patients of fibro adenoma was noticed [8]. The second most frequent benign breast disease was fibrocystic as discovered in this work. Most of the patients of this disease were in forth decade of their life. Ali [11] & Rashid [10] also concluded that fibrocystic benign breast diseases were the second most frequent disease. Stern [12] concluded this disease as most frequent in the females of every age group especially females of the Middle Ages. Chaudhary [8] in his research work of two hundred and thirty-four patients, concluded that this disease was the most common having maximum patients in the age group of 5th decade of life while Kamal concluded that sixty-five percent cases of this disease were thirty-one to fifty year of age 31-40 years [13].

Sixteen percent patients were suffering of breast abscess in this research work and the high occurrence of this disease was in the patients of third decade of life. This complication was mostly found in the lactating females after childbirth. Barton concluded in his research that bacterial mastitis was most common in the lactating breasts [16]. The percentage of other benign breast diseases was different in different age groups in this research work as well as proved by different other studies. Smoking is discovered as a common cause of mammary duct ectasia [17, 18]. But this connection of duct ectasia and smoking was not discovered in this research work. Mastalgia is the cause of 25% referral to breast surgical units in the West [3] and this disease affects seventy percent females in the lives at any time [8]. The highest rate of this disease was found in the age group of third decade of life. It is worldly acknowledged that prognosis for pure treatment with suitable anti-tuberculous therapy is outstanding to tackle these complications. The occurrence is below 0.1% of all breast abrasions in the modern countries and three to four percent in the countries which are under development [19].

CONCLUSION:

Benign breast diseases are very common abnormalities in the females who have reached at

their age of reproduction. Pain in the breast, discharge from nipples and palpable lump are the main causes of the suffering in females, therefore, most of these females visits the hospitals. The most common BBD is fibroadenoma which is found mostly in the females of having twenty-one to forty year of age. The next most frequent benign breast disease is fibrocystic and its occurrence increases with the increase of age of the female.

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